

GULEC - GUEST LECTURE APPLICATION A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The paper presented here is about GULEC that is a guest lecture web application which would help in conducting the guest lecture in colleges. For proper growth in the academic area, colleges are arranging guest lecture and all the information related to a particular guest lecture need to be stored which intern demands lots of paperwork. The organization of guest lectures is an essential part of most of the departments in the college. Today's world is a computerized world where doing all manual work will not be a good idea. Thus this application will act as helping hand for the guest lecture conductors. The application built mainly focuses on the reduction in the amount of paperwork and thus is very effective for use.

INTRODUCTION

Guest speakers have turned into a basic piece of the instructive experience for students. They help to acquaint understudies with genuine educational encounters from the situation of somebody who has been there. Students get the opportunity to see the knowledge and point of view of the Guest speaker's specific field. Different colleges ask guest speakers to the campus for a variety of reasons. A teacher can invite a successful alumnus to come to the classroom and share with students about how they broke into their field. Guest speakers can open up students eyes to openings for work they never observed conceivable. One critical preferred standpoint that is gotten from having a visitor speaker is the upgrade of the students' instructive experience. Guest speakers give something that you can't offer your students; an alternate point of view. An expert, experienced visitor speaker can truly make a solid impact on understudies. The fascinating lectures on different subjects help the certainty of new aspirants as the lectures close with persuading inquiry and answer sessions. Recognized guest instructors talk on different vital points that would demonstrate invaluable for them while picking the correct profession ways.

There are numerous ways that you can pick a potential visitor speaker for your classroom. The least demanding route is through informal. Ask your associates or send an office-wide email inquiring as to whether anybody is an appropriate possibility for the subject you require. For the most part, people exhorted are solid and have been utilized as a part of the instructive framework previously. The program is expected

to enhance students' knowledge experience by providing current and relevant examples of the practical applications of the theory they are learning in a particular subject.[1]

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The training in the medieval college was for the instructor to peruse from a unique source to a class of understudies who took notes on the address. The perusing from unique sources developed into the perusing of sparkles on a unique and after that all the for the most part to address notes. All through a lot of history, the dissemination of information by means of written by hand address notes was a basic component of scholastic life. A guest lecturer for an online class becomes a successful event, in which students get completely involved into the class, and as described, the apex in activity from them comes when the guest speaker is implicated in the class. They show their greater rate of "efficiency" by participating in all kinds of deliberation, postings, etc. It is more successful than in an actual classroom by certain aspects like one of them can be psychological. In which the student in a classroom is more reserved at the time of response to the questions, whereas in an online course there is nothing to worry, and if the topic that is spoken about is of interest of the student, involvement is more likely to happen when using this method.[2] In one of the report, it is clarified how making visitor speakers required is an extremely fruitful alternative, since it demonstrates that the outcomes are surprisingly better than anticipated; it likewise gave associations inside the bookkeeping significant students and the speakers, who were subjects in this study.[3]

As indicated by these categories, it can be seen that there is a part right in the center of students that react well to guest speakers and students who don't. The way this learning movement is utilized huge affects the students' enthusiasm for the class. There is never going to be a correct answer or a correct path on the best way to apply this once in a while utilized the method, in any case, certain measures can be taken all together for a visitor speaker occasion to have the normal outcomes for a decided classroom.

III. OBJECTIVE

The app built will be very much useful for colleges in the conduction of activities like Guest Lectures to groom their skills. Conduction of a single guest lecture depends on various factors such as venue, equipment, filling the seats, preparing the audience, preparing the guest, introduction and pre-speech talk, collect feedback form formally. The reduction in paperwork will definitely reduce the extra effort of the concerned Organizers, saving their time. The issue of paper comes here in which even a single guest lecture required a bundle of pages. So, by reducing the huge amount of paperwork and digitalizing everything we intern would help the society.

IV. WORKING

The app built will be efficient in the conduction of the guest lectures in colleges. It would work in the following modules:-

MODULE 1: In the first module, the app will open with the login page where there is an option for the login of admin and admin will give authority to sub admin for registering the students.

MODULE 2: After registration of students the guest teacher will be invited by an invitation letter through the mail which means our application is interfaced with mailing gateway.

MODULE 3: In return for the invitation, the guest teacher would reply through the mail which shows the acceptance and would initiate the conduction of the guest lecture.

MODULE 4: A QR code would be generated and sent to the mail ids of the registered students. The students would use that QR code to login and attend the guest lecture.

MODULE 5: As soon as the guest lecture session ends, the students would be required to fill feedback forms which would lead to the generation of a report.

V.CONCLUSION

Hence, the application built would be very much useful to the students and in addition the teachers .The app would be very much beneficial in reducing time and better utilization of human resources. The time spent for the documentation can be utilized for other useful works. In addition to the problem of time, the app solves one of the major issues arising the paperwork which would help in saving the trees.With the help of this project the guest lectures can be conducted with ease.

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